

ODD Protocol

Purpose

The primary objective of this model is to simulate the transfer and settlement stages of dispersal on heterogeneous landscapes, taking into account different levels of plasticity in habitat selection during settlement, which are based on the habitat quality threshold that an individual accepts to settle in the new habitat. Therefore, we investigate the effect of the interaction of plasticity on habitat selection, landscape composition, configuration, dispersal movement, and settlement success.

Entities, state variables and scales

❖ The landscape

The landscape has a cell grid of 300 x 300 (-150,+150), each representing 10m². The interface can change these values by defining world size and patch resolution. The landscape is characterised by cover type, which means habitat patches (cover = 1) or a matrix of pasture or non-habitat (cover = 0). Landscapes used in this study have compositions varying by the percentage of habitat amount, from 5 to 70%, and "clumpiness" (degree of clustering), from 15 to 100%. Each habitat cell is also characterised by habitat quality (Q: 0~1), representing the amount of resources available, and the habitat quality of matrix cells is zero. Habitat-quality surfaces can be generated by different methods, which will be explained later. Additionally, each patch has an identification (ID) and a distance value from other habitat patches (DIST). We generated the layers used in the simulation for cover and DIST at GRASS GIS (Neteler et al. 2012) in ASCII format and imported these to the NetLogo environment. These state variables are presented below in Table S2.1.

Table S2.1: Patches state variables of the model

State variables	Description
<i>Landscape</i>	
Cover type	Type of cover: habitat patches (cover = 1) and matrix of pasture or non-habitat (cover = 0).
Habitat Quality (Q)	The amount of resources available varies from 0 to 1. The quality of matrix patches is zero (0).
Fragment identification (ID)	ID of the fragment where the patch is included.
Distance from habitat patches (DIST)	Distance from the patch and the nearest habitat patch. Habitat patches DIST is always zero (0).

❖ The agents

The agents are small mammals with different levels of plasticity on habitat selection throughout dispersal. Initially, this model was developed to simulate three species of marsupials (*D. aurita*, *P. quica* and *M. paraguayana*). However, it can be adapted to any other species. Each marsupial is characterised by the state variables presented in Table S2.2. By defining which species will be simulated at each simulation, the model imports the variables regarding perceptual range (PR) and movement parameters, such as parameters for distributions of step length and turning angles, specifically for the species to be simulated. Check the input section for more details on the species' input data.

Table S2.2: Individuals' state variables of the model

State variables	Variable over time?	Definition/ Update	Description
Identification (ID)	No	Beginning	Number of identification
Initial Patch	No	Beginning	ID of the initial patch before starting to disperse.
Status	Yes	Beginning and Settlement	Disperser (dis) or Settler (set). They start as dispersers and become settlers when they finally find a new habitat to settle.
Level of Plasticity (e_C)	No	Beginning	Any positive value (zero means no plasticity). In our case, from 0 to 2, a 0.5 interval.
Initial Habitat Quality Threshold (Ci)	No	Beginning	Initial value of habitat quality threshold accepted by the individual in the new habitat. Two ways can calculate that: (1) If the 'origin site' button is true, then Ci equals the habitat quality in the initial patch. (2) Calculated as a random value based on a minimal Ci (min_Ci) and variation Ci (var_Ci) values, defined in the interface. Then the values will be random from min_Ci up to (min_Ci + var_Ci).
Habitat Quality Threshold (C)	Yes	Every step	The habitat quality threshold accepted by the individual in the new habitat at every step.
The minimum energy required (min_en)	No	Beginning	Minimum energy required by the individual to keep dispersing. Below this value, the individual will be forced to settle. Gaussian Distribution: mean = 0.2, standard deviation = 0.1
Energetic condition (En)	Yes	Every step	Energetic condition of the individual at every step of the simulation
Habitat quality within perceptual range (H')	Yes	Every step	The mean of habitat quality (Q) of the cells within the individual's perceptual range
Decision	Yes	Settlement	If the decision to settle was based on habitat quality (H) or energy (En)
Total Euclidean distance (linear_dist)	No	End	Total linear distance in metres by an individual during dispersal
Total distance moved (total_dist)	Yes	Every step	Total distance in metres moved by an individual during dispersal

Process overview

The model simulates the transfer and settlement stages of dispersal in fragmented landscapes. Figure S2 provides a detailed flow diagram of the model simulation. In the following

sections, we explained every step of the model and then presented detailed explanations of movement characterisation, energetic dynamics and habitat selection behaviours.

❖ Parametrisation and configuration

Before starting the model, the parameters and configurations in the interface must be defined. The respective initial parameters to create the world to be simulated are: world size, which defines the number of cells to be simulated, patch resolution, which is how much each cell represents in metres, and size, which is the size to visualise the cell. The initial parameters to create the individuals are species, which defines the species to be simulated, individuals, the number of individuals to simulate, perceptual range, and the distance in metres of perceptual range, which is species-specific. Then, regarding movement, it is necessary to define the value of mortality in the matrix and habitat and the minimal distance the individual needs to move before deciding to settle. The directories for importing landscape, input data and saving the output must be defined. Besides those, configuration and parameters regarding the initial habitat quality threshold (C_i), energetic dynamics, and habitat quality surface generation are also defined in the interface. These are explained later in the following sections.

❖ Habitat quality surface

The habitat quality surface can be implemented in four ways:

1. Importing the habitat quality layer from a specific folder. In this case, it is necessary to match with landscape size and resolution files;
2. Generate a random value of habitat quality from 0 to 1 per fragment in the landscape. In this case, all patches in the same fragment will have the same value of habitat quality;
3. Generate a habitat quality surface independently of the fragment but with spatial autocorrelation. In this case, two ways are implemented to define the autocorrelation. In both ways, autocorrelation is determined based on the number of neighbouring patches. However, in a simple way, check the patch and its eight neighbour patches

to define similar values if autocorrelation is high. The complex way, check per patch, which generates a more detailed autocorrelation, but turns the model slow when the world size is higher than 100.

❖ Movement characterisation

Movement rules in the matrix were implemented similarly to Rocha et al. (2021) as a discrete model consisting of a discrete series of steps and events of reorientation and described by Lévy flights, with a Gaussian distribution for turning angles and a Pareto truncated distribution for step lengths. The parameters which control the model were the minimum step length (ℓ_{\min}), maximum step length (ℓ_{\max}), exponent for the Pareto truncated distribution (μ), and the mean and standard deviation for the Gaussian distribution of turning angles. Parameter estimates varied by species and whether the movement was oriented or non-oriented to any landscape element. These parameters are included in the species' input file. Movement rules in the habitat followed a similar implementation for step length and turning angles. However, due to the lack of empirical data on movement within habitat fragments for the species of marsupials simulated, and aiming to simulate a more tortuous and shorter movement in comparison with matrix movement, values of parameters for step length were similar to the ones of non-oriented movement in the matrix, when steps are shorter, and for turning angles a gaussian distribution with mean equal to 0 (zero) and standard deviation equal to 90 (ninety). Because of that, the parameters of the movement in the habitat are not included in the species' input file but are defined directly in the code. These parameters can be adapted to any species.

❖ Energetic dynamics

Each individual starts the simulation with an energetic condition (E_n) equal to 1. At every step of the dispersal movement, the individual expends energy while moving proportionally to the distance moved during dispersal. The energy expenditure is calculated based on a discharge rate, which is double in the matrix than in the habitat, representing the possibility of feeding and resting while dispersing within habitat fragments. At every movement step, the energy deducted from E_n is

calculated by multiplying the discharge rate and the logarithm of the total distance moved. Each individual has a minimal energetic condition value (min_En) to keep dispersing, which is defined by a Gaussian distribution with parameters indicated by a mean (En_mean) and a standard deviation (En_sd) specified in the interface. When the individual reaches that energy level, it will settle on the next habitat regardless of its habitat quality.

❖ Habitat selection behaviours

Each individual has a habitat selection threshold (C), which means that the individual will settle when it finds a new habitat with equal or higher habitat quality than its threshold or reaches the minimal energetic condition. The initial habitat quality threshold (C_i) can be defined in two ways: If the ‘origin site’ button in the interface is ‘on’, then the C_i is equal to the habitat quality in the initial patch of the individual. If that button is ‘off’, C_i is calculated as a random value based on the minimal C_i (min_C_i) and variation C_i (var_C_i) values defined in the interface. Then the values will be random from min_C_i up to ($min_C_i + var_C_i$).

At every step, the individual updates the C values based on its energetic condition (En), which expresses the plasticity in the selection habitat during settlement. At every step in dispersal, the individual expends energy, and its energetic condition decreases; then the habitat quality threshold also decreases. This relationship might change its intensity, which is based on the exponent of the function (e_C), representing different levels of plasticity (Figure S1). The non-plastic behaviour is represented when the $e_C = 0$, and the C does not decrease with the reduction of the energetic condition. That is calculated based on the following equation:

Figure S1: Relationship between the energetic condition (En) and habitat quality threshold (C) regarding plasticity levels (e_C).

The values of e_C to be simulated are defined on the interface by informing the initial, interval and final values, then it will generate a list with all the values from the initial to the final by the interval defined.

❖ Scheduling of the model

The environment is created in the setup by importing the landscape files and generating the habitat quality surface (details are presented in the sub-models section). After that, the individuals are created and distributed randomly across the landscape in habitat patches. The simulation starts with all individuals moving to the matrix and starting the dispersal movement regarding the transfer stage. At every step of the simulation, the individual checks his energy condition. When it reaches 0, the individual dies. Otherwise, he updates his variables, the mean habitat quality within perceptual range (H') and habitat quality threshold (C). Then, the individual will disperse regardless of the cover of the cell he is in until he moves a distance (D') more than the minimal dispersal distance defined. After that step, if he is in the matrix, he will keep dispersing, but when he reaches a habitat cell, he needs to decide whether to settle or not. The simulation stops if the individual decides to settle, otherwise, he will keep dispersing. The decision to settle is based on the mean habitat quality perceptual range (H'), the energetic condition (En) and the habitat quality threshold (C). The settlement will occur if H' is higher than C, which means that the habitat quality

in the area is equal to or higher than the required for the individual, or if E_n is lower than the minimal energetic condition to disperse (min_E_n), which means that the individual has no energetic condition to keep dispersing.

The *disperse* submodel is detailed on the right of Figure S2. Within this process, the individual will select the step length and turning angle from the respective distribution according to the cover of the patch and orientation. If the individual is in a habitat patch and decides not to settle, then he will draw the parameters from the distribution of movement in the habitat. If the individual is in the matrix and any habitat patch is within his perceptual range, then he will be oriented in the matrix toward the habitat patch, or if no habitat patch is encountered within his perceptual range, then he is non-oriented in the matrix. In this case, the individual will draw the parameters from the distribution of movement in the matrix, oriented or non-oriented. Details are presented in the movement characterisation section. Afterwards, the individual calculates the new coordinates based on the turning angle and step lengths drawn from the distributions, moves to that location and then updates the total distance moved (D'). At that point, the individual expends energy proportional to the distance moved and faces the chance of mortality. The mortality chance is calculated at every movement step across the habitat and the matrix. Due to the lack of empirical data regarding mortality, the mortality rate values for habitat and matrix were calibrated to represent a dangerous matrix, a less dangerous habitat, and not enough threats to kill all individuals. The simulation stops when all individuals are settled or dead.

Figure S2: Flow diagram of the individual-based model describing decisions faced by individuals in the simulation

Design Concepts

❖ Basic principles

The model intends to understand how different behaviours on the disperser's decision to settle affect the success of dispersal and how this effect changes in heterogeneous landscapes, varying composition and configuration. The individual decision is based on a trade-off between habitat quality and the body's energetic condition in habitat selection. A movement in the matrix is based on the perceptual range as an orientation aspect.

❖ Emergence

This model is expected to produce two main emerging results. First, the effect of plasticity on dispersal through the trade-off between habitat quality and energetic condition in the settlement decision. Second, by simulating different landscape compositions and configurations, another result

expected is the interaction of that trade-off with the landscape, exposing the possible impacts of habitat loss and fragmentation on dispersal.

❖ Adaptation

Individuals have to move and search for a new habitat to settle. The decision to settle is based on the habitat quality threshold, by which the individual will settle in a habitat with equal or higher quality. However, the search can be interrupted by the lower energetic condition of the individual, who expends energy during movement. Besides that, during the movement in the matrix, individuals seek a habitat by searching the area within its perceptual range and get oriented towards a fragment when it find one.

❖ Objective

The main objective of the individuals in this model is to find a new and good-quality habitat to settle.

❖ Learning

Over time, individuals with plasticity change its selectivity by decreasing its habitat quality threshold and accepting to settle in lower-quality habitats.

❖ Prediction

Individual decision-making is based on the information gathered within its perceptual range. It can search for new habitat fragments and gather information on the area's average habitat quality.

❖ Interaction

There is no interaction among the agents.

❖ Stochasticity

The initial location of agents, the initial habitat quality threshold, and the minimal energy to keep dispersing vary among the individuals. The habitat quality values of patches consider also a variation, however, it is generated with a spatial correlation. The movement step lengths and turning angles are drawn from distributions, resulting also in a variation.

Details

❖ Initialisation

The individuals are randomly distributed across all habitat patches in the landscape, and the total number of individuals per patch is proportional to its size. Depending on the simulated landscape's habitat amount and clumpiness parameters, the landscape presents a combination of cover types, such as matrix and habitat patches.

❖ Input data

Simulated landscape layers were generated and imported as ASCII files. Text files imported species' parameters and landscape values of clumpiness and habitat amount.

❖ Output

At the end of the simulations, two output files are created, the `sim_parameters.txt` and the `output.txt`. In the first file, all fixed variables are registered together with the number of simulations. The second file registered individual initial and final variables for all successful settlers, such as identification, initial patch and its identification, minimal energetic condition to disperse, initial and final habitat quality threshold, level of plasticity, coordinates, the energetic condition of the individual when he is settled, the habitat quality of the settlement area, the decision to settle, the total distance moved and the euclidian distance from the start patch and the final patch in the settlement area.

Besides that main output, it is possible to generate an output of movement parameters, step length and turning angles for all steps and all individuals, and also a path output, which will generate an output with the coordinates of a specific number of individuals (defined in `N_path`). Also, an occupancy output is available, providing a file with a list of paths occupied by individuals with different plasticity levels.